

LATENCY-CONTROLLED AUTOMATIC CHORD RECOGNITION WITH CONTEXTUAL BLOCK PROCESSING TRANSFORMER

Chih-Cheng CHANG (ccchang12@iis.sinica.edu.tw)¹ and Li SU (lisu@iis.sinica.edu.tw)¹

¹*Institute of Information Science, Academia Sinica, Taipei, Taiwan*

ABSTRACT

Interest in musical co-creativity has increased with the advancements in artificial intelligence recently. Despite the importance of collaborative real-time musical performance applications, the online analysis of abstract and descriptive musical features, such as chords and harmony, emerges as a critical task. Despite its importance, real-time automatic chord recognition (ACR) remains a challenging task due to the inherent uncertainty of future data. This paper presents a novel approach to real-time ACR, utilizing contextual block processing (CBP) encoders designed for online scenarios. The CBP encoder ensures latency-controlled recognition with enhanced accuracy by attending to look-ahead frames. Furthermore, our method capitalizes on the intrinsic hierarchical and functional relationships within the chords to enhance model training. Experimental results on music audio recordings demonstrate the superior performance of our model over state-of-the-art real-time ACR systems. In particular, our model shows only a relative accuracy degradation of 1.3% compared to offline baseline models, with a latency of 186 ms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, specifically the Transformer architecture and its variants [1], have improved the performance of various music information retrieval (MIR) tasks, including beat tracking [2–4], automatic chord recognition (ACR) [5–7], and transcription [8–10]. Besides from their various MIR applications, such advancements have strengthened expectations for the next generation of AI-powered musical co-creativity applications, such as automatic music accompaniment, interactive music performance, and auto DJ [11–13]. In some specific scenarios such as human-machine collaborative improvisation, real-time ACR is needed when chord information is not predetermined, requiring the machine to detect the chord progression of the music being performed by the human musician in nearly real time.

Previous studies of real-time ACR have focused on lightweight implementations such as hidden Markov models (HMMs) [14] or template-based approaches with effective

chroma feature calculation [15]. A trade-off between recognition and system latency was also reported in [14]. On the other hand, the development of offline ACR technology in recent years has primarily focused on neural networks. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [16, 17], convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [18, 19], convolutional recurrent neural networks (CRNNs) [20], and Transformers [5–7] have all demonstrated their effectiveness in offline ACR, and apparently become a new opportunity for the development of online ACR. Among these models, the Transformer, renowned for its state-of-the-art performance in numerous tasks, is especially noticeable. However, deploying Transformers for streaming applications is not easy. Transformer models face limitations in online processing since they require the entire input sequence for attention computation. This introduces high computational complexity and latency, hindering their application in real-time MIR tasks.¹

Recently, the contextual block processing (CBP) mechanism within the Transformer encoder has been noticed as a streamable solution for Transformer-based models [21]. With the CBP mechanism of the encoder, the output can be produced by giving partially available music audio frames rather than the entire input sequence. This facilitates latency-controlled recognition by assessing various look-ahead sizes under different latency constraints, which is the crucial feature for streaming applications. CBP and similar block processing mechanisms have been utilized in a number of streaming scenarios for audio, including speech recognition [22], speech separation, and music beat/downbeat detection [3].

In this paper, we propose an online ACR model based on the CBP Transformer. The CBP Transformer processes audio streams in blocks with musically meaningful sizes, without the need of the entire sequence as input. The context embedding vector of the CBP block encodes both local (i.e. current) and global (i.e. preceding) musical context in the online recognition process, an aspect often overlooked in existing online ACR systems. Besides, we incorporate relationships between chord labels and employ musical knowledge-based loss functions for optimization.

¹ In this work, we adopt the term *real-time* following its commonly accepted usage in the *real-time* systems community: *real-time* refers to online systems with finite look-ahead, where the value of the computed result decreases over time. In the simplest scenario, this value remains constant up to a certain deadline, after which it becomes zero. Hence, our approach to Automatic Chord Recognition (ACR) should be viewed as *latency-controlled*, emphasizing timely predictions within acceptable latency constraints. Consequently, *real-time* ACR inherently involves a trade-off between latency and accuracy, underscoring the importance of managing latency rather than attempting to achieve absolute zero latency.

Evaluation of our proposed model on real-world pop music datasets demonstrates a superior performance compared to state-of-the-art online methods, as well as comparable performance to offline methods. Notably, even at a low latency of 186 ms,² our model shows only a 1.3% relative accuracy degradation compared to offline baseline models, outperforming existing online methods. In addition, through ablation studies, we provide insight into the effectiveness of context embedding vectors and chord label relationships in enhancing ACR performance.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Automatic Chord Recognition

An ACR system typically incorporates three stages: audio feature extraction, pattern matching, and chord sequence decoding. First, for audio feature extraction, music signals are transformed into a time-frequency representation, such as spectrograms or chromagrams. With the rise of deep neural network (DNN), efforts have been made to improve feature representation through DNN-based chroma feature estimators [24]. In the pattern matching stage, the extracted features are classified using either rule-based chord template algorithms or a data-driven model. Rule-based methods offer speed and reasonable accuracy [14, 15], yet the ascent of deep learning has ushered in a shift toward data-driven approaches in ACR. Finally, a post-processing stage involving probabilistic graphical models is applied to decode the chord sequence. HMMs and conditional random fields (CRFs) [25] are commonly employed to predict chord progressions. However, most of the existing decoding approaches are typically designed for non-causal offline processing, requiring access to future data, rendering them unsuitable for real-time applications. Cho and Bello addressed this issue by adjusting HMMs through the utilization of chroma vector representation for real-time applications [14].

2.2 Transformer for Online Scenarios

The Transformer presents a challenge on online processing due to its requirement of processing the entire input sequence for self-attention, rendering it impractical for real-time applications in online processing systems. Several solutions have been proposed to alleviate this constraint. One solution is the time-restricted multi-head attention, where the attention computation utilizes only past input vectors and a limited number of look-ahead frames [26]. However, this method often introduces substantial latency due to the linear growth of the receptive field with the number of transformer layers. Recent investigations have explored alternative strategies for online processing of the attention mechanism, such as window shifting using the median [27] or employing monotonic energy functions as in MoChA [28]. Furthermore, adaptations of the Transformer model, such as the self-attention aligner [29]

² It was reported that human reaction time for major/minor chord recognition is 0.85-1 seconds [23]. Therefore, we consider 186ms as a satisfactory latency value for the application scenarios that needs real-time ACR.

and contextual block processing Transformer [21], have proposed chunk-hopping mechanisms to support online speech recognition. Similar methods have been explored in the augmented memory Transformer (AM-TRF) [30] and efficient memory Transformer (Emformer) [31], which incorporates augmented memory banks along with partitioning of the input speech sequence for online automatic speech recognition application.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Contextual Block Processing Transformer

A Transformer encoder model with contextual block processing (CBP) based on the chunk-hopping mechanism has been proposed to make the Transformer capable of the online scenario [29]. However, it loses information about the global context and degrades performance in general. In this work, we adopt the CBP mechanism in [21] that utilizes block processing with a context inheritance mechanism. The CBP mechanism is introduced as follows.

First, the entire sequence of input feature vectors is segmented into several non-overlapping segments $C := \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_b, \dots\}$. C_b represents the b^{th} current frames, where b is the block index, and each block contains N_c current frames. To reduce the boundary effect in forming the contextual block, for each C_b we introduce the left and right sub-blocks as the *history* and *look-ahead* frames, namely L_b and R_b , respectively, where L_b is an N_l -frame segment before C_b , and R_b is an N_r -frame segment after C_b . The numbers N_l , N_c , and N_r are all positive integers. Concatenating them forms a contextual block $z_b^n = [L_b, C_b, R_b]$ as the input for the n^{th} layer of the CBP encoder. Fig. 1 illustrates a simple example where $N_c = 2$ and $N_l = N_r = 1$.

Furthermore, for each block z_b^n , an additional context embedding vector c_b^n inherited from the previous block is utilized in each layer of each block to capture the long-term dependency of the input sequence. With the additional context embedding vector, the input query, key, and value of the multi-head attention (MHA) layer are represented as $\tilde{q}_b^1 = \tilde{k}_b^1 = \tilde{v}_b^1 = [z_b^0, c_b^0]$ in the first layer ($n = 1$), where $\tilde{\cdot}$ denotes the augmented variables with the context embedding vector. The initial context embedding vector c_b^0 is defined as the average of the input sequence for the block z_b^0 to inherit global statistics from preceding blocks. In the succeeding layers ($n > 1$), $\tilde{q}_b^n = [z_b^{n-1}, c_b^{n-1}]$ and $\tilde{k}_b^n = \tilde{v}_b^n = [z_b^{n-1}, c_{b-1}^{n-1}]$ are similarly augmented with the context embedding vector c_{b-1}^{n-1} in the previous block ($b - 1$) of the previous layer ($n - 1$) and z_b^{n-1} .

Both the vanilla Transformer and the original CBP encoder employ deterministic sinusoidal functions to encode absolute positions [1, 21]. However, music has multiple dimensions along which relative differences matter more than their absolute values. To capture pairwise positional relationships, several methods have modulated self-attention with a position relation-aware mechanism [32, 33]. Since the original relative positional encoding cannot be directly applied to the CBP encoder due to the necessity of computing pairwise relationships across the

Figure 1. The illustration of contextual block processing encoder. The input vector is represented by colored blocks: blue blocks represent the contextual block z_b , orange blocks represent the context embedding vector from the present block and inherited from the previous block.

entire input sequence, we introduce a modified approach that calculates pairwise relationships only within each contextual block. We integrate the relative positional encoding introduced in [33] into our CBP encoder. By introducing additional bias terms for queries and utilizing sinusoidal formulation for relative position encoding, the attention scores A_b between two arbitrary positions i and j within each block of the input sequence are

$$A_{b,i,j} := Q_{b,i}K_{b,j}^\top + Q_{b,i}W_R^\top R_{i-j}^\top + uK_{b,j}^\top + vW_R^\top R_{i-j}^\top, \quad (1)$$

where the added item R_{i-j} is the sinusoid encoding vectors providing the prior of relative position, and $W_R \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a trainable matrix projecting R_{i-j} into a location-based key vector. The two bias terms $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are both trainable vectors.

Fig.1 illustrates the complete architecture of the CBP encoder. The relative positional embedding is first applied to each contextual block with the context embedding vector. Each layer consists of two sub-layers: MHA and a position-wise feed-forward layer. The residual connections are placed across each sub-layer, perform layer normalization [34] before and dropout [35] after each sub-layer.

3.2 Chord Distance

In many existing ACR works, the relationships between individual chord classes are often overlooked in computing the loss function. In this work, we leverage the approach proposed in [19] that accounts for the interrelations among different chord labels. We choose the Tonnetz-space, a geometric representation of the tonal space derived from chord harmonic relationships, to quantify the relationships between various chord labels [36]. Tonnetz-space is constructed through three transformations of the major and mi-

nor triads, each changing only one of the three notes in the triad: 1) relative transformation, 2) parallel transformation, and 3) leading-tone exchange. The cost of a path between two chords in this space is determined as the cumulative sum of successive transformations, with each transformation incurring the same cost. The chord distance D is defined as the shortest path (in terms of the number of transformations) between two chords within the Tonnetz-space:

$$D(\text{chord}_1, \text{chord}_2) := \min(C), \quad (2)$$

where C represents the set of all feasible path costs from chord_1 to chord_2 using a combination of the transformations [19]. To optimize the loss function with the distance of the chord, a symmetric similarity matrix M that associates each pair of chords to a similarity ratio is introduced. The (i, j) th element of M is represented as

$$M_{i,j} := \frac{1}{D(\text{chord}_i, \text{chord}_j) + \epsilon}, \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is an arbitrary constant to avoid division by zero. The normalized similarity matrix, \hat{M} , is a normalization of M by its maximum value. To apply the chord distance in our model, we use a 25-dimensional target vector y_{target} which is a one-hot representation of the ground truth, encompassing 24 chord classes (12 major and 12 minor chords) and a "No chord" class. The multi-label vector y'_{target} is then computed as:

$$y'_{\text{target}} := y_{\text{target}}\hat{M}. \quad (4)$$

This y'_{target} serves as our weighted ground truth, incorporating chord relationships into the model's learning process. The loss function then compares this weighted multi-label y'_{target} with the model's output, effectively creating a weighted multi-label classification problem that accounts for chord similarities.

3.3 Complete Architecture

Our model for online ACR processes audio input through several stages. The audio (with a sampling rate of 22,050 Hz) is first transformed using constant Q transform (CQT) with 6 octaves starting from C1, 24 bins per octave, with a hop size of 93 ms (2048 samples). The CQT features are transformed to log amplitude with $S_{\text{log}} = \ln(S + \epsilon)$ where S represents the CQT feature and $\epsilon = 1e-6$ is a small constant for numerical stability. After that, global z-normalization is applied with the mean and variance of the training data. Before the CBP encoder blocks, three 2D convolutional and max pooling layers are utilized as the front-end feature extractor that maps the 144-dimensional input features to 256-dimensional vectors.

The model has nine layers of CBP encoders. Each encoder layer has eight heads of block processing self-attention network followed by a position-wise feedforward network with hidden dimension = 1,024, both of which have residual connections. Finally, the output of the CBP encoder layers is fed into a fully-connected layer followed by a sigmoid activation to predict the probability distribution over the chord vocabulary for each frame.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Dataset

Our model is evaluated on three audio datasets. First, the Isophonics³ dataset comprises 179 songs by the Beatles, 7 songs by Carole King, 20 songs by Queen, and 18 songs by Zweieck. The second dataset comprises 65 songs by Robbie Williams [37]. The third dataset is a subset of 191 songs from UsPop2002⁴. These datasets were accompanied by label files that specify the start time, end time, and type of the chord. Since exact audio file replication was unfeasible, leading to subtle differences in chord start times between label and audio files, we manually shift the entire label file backward or forward to achieve alignment with the audio file. Additionally, for data augmentation purposes, pitch shifting of all the training data from -5 to +6 semitones was implemented using the pyrubberband⁵ package. The labels were correspondingly modified to reflect the pitch variations. 5-fold cross-validation was applied to the entire dataset.

For ground truth labeling, we adopted the “maj-min” label type that contains a total of 25 chord labels, including all major and minor chords (12 semitones maj, min) along with a “No chord” category. Chords corresponding to the input feature’s time frame were extracted from label files and transformed into the appropriate label type for model training and evaluation.

4.2 Training

We employ the binary cross-entropy loss function for chord prediction, incorporating the chord distance described in section 3.2. The loss function $L_{\text{BCE}} := (y_{\text{pred}}, y'_{\text{target}})$ compares predicted probabilities y_{pred} with weighted multi-label targets y'_{target} derived from Equation (4). Music data is segmented into 10-second clips. We optimize our model using the RAdam [38] plus Lookahead [39] optimizer, initializing with a learning rate of $2e-4$. This learning rate is dynamically adjusted, reducing by a factor of 5 if validation loss stagnates for 5 consecutive epochs, while maintaining a minimum value of $1e-7$. Dropout regularization with a rate of 0.25 is applied across all components of the network to prevent overfitting. With a total of 7.54M trainable parameters each training fold converges after approximately 20 epochs.

4.3 Evaluation Metrics

Evaluation of ACR incorporates two key aspects: 1) frame-wise chord recognition accuracy and 2) chord segmentation quality. The former evaluates the model’s ability to predict chords accurately at the frame level, while the latter examines the predicted chord sequences from a chord segmentation perspective. The evaluation metric for the accuracy of chord recognition is the weighted chord symbol recall (WCSR) score. The WCSR score is computed as $WCSR := t_c/t$, where t_c is the duration of correctly

classified chord segments and t is the duration of the entire chord segments. The “root” and “maj-min” scores are calculated using the mir_eval library [40] to evaluate the performance of chord recognition.

For chord segmentation quality, we utilize the directional Hamming distance (DHD) [41] to evaluate the segmentation quality (SQ)

$$SQ := 1 - \frac{\max(\text{DHD}(S, \hat{S}), \text{DHD}(\hat{S}, S))}{t}, \quad (5)$$

where S denotes the annotated segmentation, \hat{S} denotes the predicted segmentation, and t denotes the total duration of the song. The SQ value reflects the similarity of two segmentations, with higher values indicating better segmentation quality.

In real-time systems, a critical consideration is finding a balance between latency and performance. Regarding latency, we focus on the algorithmic latency encountered by the model architecture. Algorithmic latency refers to the total number of frames that a model must observe at each prediction step to make a prediction, which includes both current input frames and a limited number of future frames for look-ahead. For clarity, we explicitly define the latency of our proposed CBP-based models as the sum of the current block frame size (N_c) and the look-ahead frame size (N_r). In contrast, the latency of baseline CNN [18] and CRNN [20] models is defined by the sum of current block frame size and minimum number of future frames required due to the inherent non-causality of the convolutional or recurrent layers.

4.4 Results

We selected two baseline models for comparison: “CNN+CRF” from [18], consisting of eight layers of CNN with an additional CRF chord decoder, and BTC [6], a model based on the bidirectional transformer encoder. Both baseline models were trained on our dataset to establish offline references. Given the relative lack of emphasis on online ACR, we selected the same CNN model in [18] without the CRF decoder and the CRNN model detailed in [20], where the bidirectional gated recurrent unit (GRU) was replaced with a unidirectional GRU, to serve as our online baseline models.

In our experiments, we keep the left context size $N_l = 32$. To investigate the performance of latency-controlled ACR, we vary the algorithmic latency by adjusting N_c and N_r . Our experience suggests that keeping N_c and N_r the same can lead to better performance within latency constraints. Table 1 shows the validation scores of the baseline models and our models at different latencies. We denote models with different look-ahead sizes N_r as “CBP- N_r ”. Our proposed model outperforms all the online baseline models in all metrics, particularly segmentation quality, even at a comparable latency. In particular, substantial enhancements in segmentation quality persist even with a latency of less than 0.2 seconds. This can be attributed to the selective utilization of attention in self-attention mechanisms, wherein the history frames in the CBP encoder establish

³ <http://isophonics.net/datasets>

⁴ <https://github.com/tmc323/Chord-Annotations>

⁵ <https://github.com/bmcfee/pyrubberband>

Offline Methods														
Model	Latency (s)	Robbie Williams			Isophonics			UsPop2002			Total			
		root	maj/min	SQ	root	maj/min	SQ	root	maj/min	SQ	root	maj/min	SQ	
CNN+CRF [18]	—	85.05	83.86	84.63	86.27	85.44	81.16	80.29	76.86	79.35	83.00	80.94	80.83	
BTC [6]	—	86.60	82.99	87.44	84.61	83.65	83.85	82.42	79.16	82.18	83.72	81.36	83.67	

Online Methods														
CNN [18]	0.743	84.48	81.98	82.60	83.81	81.41	79.73	82.22	79.32	79.33	82.98	80.41	80.00	
CRNN [20]	0.279	83.86	81.67	81.63	83.16	80.21	78.17	81.10	77.78	78.46	82.13	79.19	78.85	
CBP-8	1.486	85.05	82.53	85.94	84.17	81.50	82.75	82.93	<u>80.01</u>	82.52	83.54	80.85	83.15	
CBP-4	0.743	84.62	81.66	85.30	83.99	80.85	82.37	82.42	80.11	81.66	83.17	80.50	82.50	
CBP-2	0.372	84.58	81.97	85.17	83.87	80.96	82.31	82.55	79.60	81.12	83.17	80.36	82.22	
CBP-1	0.186	84.79	81.35	85.08	83.74	80.79	81.94	82.02	79.41	80.63	82.91	80.26	82.83	

Table 1. Evaluation results on all datasets. Total is the average score of all datasets. (**bold**: best score, underline: second best score)

Model	Total		
	root	maj/min	SQ
w/o chord distance	83.24	80.26	82.94
w/o ctx_emb	82.92	80.25	82.92
CBP-8	83.54	80.85	83.15

Table 2. Effect of context embedding vector (ctx_emb) and chord distance on ACR performance.

an adaptive receptive field, a departure from the fixed kernel size of CNNs. Notably, our models achieve comparable performance to offline methods with latencies below 0.8 seconds, which is faster than the 0.85-1 second reaction time observed in human with musical training for major/minor chord recognition [23]. This demonstrates the potential of our approach for enhancing real-time musical applications. Further investigating individual metrics, we observed comparable performance compared to offline methods in root scores even with latencies below 0.2 seconds, while major / minor scores exhibited more degradation. This discrepancy stems from the fact that in most music, the root note typically appears at the beginning of the chord segment, contributing to well-predicted root scores even with low latencies. In contrast, the 3rd note, crucial to determining the major/minor status of the chord, sometimes appears later in a chord segment.

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed method in this work, we compared two ablation models. The first ablation model, CBP-8, was trained without considering chord relations or targets (w/o chord distance). The second model removed the context embedding vector in CBP-8 (w/o ctx_emb). In Table 2, we can observe that the proposed model yields better performance than the other two models.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, we present a novel approach to online ACR using a Transformer model with CBP mechanism. Our method achieves superior accuracy in online scenarios,

providing latency-controlled chord recognition and facilitating robust and responsive MIR systems. By utilizing contextual information and chord relationships, our model enhances ACR performance, outperforming existing online methods. This work introduces a Transformer-based framework suitable for online ACR tasks, contributing towards addressing latency and accuracy trade-offs in real-time MIR applications. Furthermore, it lays the foundation for innovative collaborative musical interactions, particularly in the realm of human-computer co-creation and generative applications. Future research may explore optimizations and extensions, fostering greater collaboration and innovation in music creation and performance within the evolving landscape of AI-driven musical co-creativity.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, “Attention is all you need,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2017, pp. 5998–6008.
- [2] J. Zhao, G. Xia, and Y. Wang, “Beat transformer: Demixed beat and downbeat tracking with dilated self-attention,” in *Proc. of the 23rd Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2022.
- [3] C.-C. Chang and L. Su, “Beast: Online joint beat and downbeat tracking based on streaming transformer,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2023, pp. 396–400.
- [4] Y.-N. Hung, J.-C. Wang, X. Song, W.-T. Lu, and M. Won, “Modeling beats and downbeats with a time-frequency transformer,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2022, pp. 401–405.
- [5] T.-P. Chen and L. Su, “Harmony transformer: Incorporating chord segmentation into harmony recognition,” in *Proc. of the 20th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2019.

- [6] J. Park, K. Choi, S. Jeon, D. Kim, and J. Park, “A bi-directional transformer for musical chord recognition,” in *Proc. of the 20th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2019.
- [7] W.-T. Lu, J.-C. Wang, M. Won, K. Choi, and X. Song, “Spectnt: A time-frequency transformer for music audio,” in *Proc. of the 22nd Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2021.
- [8] C. Hawthorne, I. Simon, R. Swavely, E. Manilow, and J. Engel, “Sequence-to-sequence piano transcription with transformers,” in *Proc. of the 22nd Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2021.
- [9] L. Ou, Z. Guo, E. Benetos, J. Han, and Y. Wang, “Exploring transformer’s potential on automatic piano transcription,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2022, pp. 776–780.
- [10] K. Toyama, T. Akama, Y. Ikemiya, Y. Takida, W.-H. Liao, and Y. Mitsufuji, “Automatic piano transcription with hierarchical frequency-time transformer,” in *Proc. of the 24th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2023.
- [11] P. M. Brossier, “Automatic annotation of musical audio for interactive applications,” Ph.D. dissertation, Queen Mary University, London, UK, 2006.
- [12] N. Jiang, S. Jin, Z. Duan, and C. Zhang, “RI-duet: Online music accompaniment generation using deep reinforcement learning,” in *Proc. of the AAAI Conf. on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI)*, 2020, pp. 710–718.
- [13] T. Carsault, J. Nika, P. Esling, and G. Assayag, “Combining real-time extraction and prediction of musical chord progressions for creative applications,” *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 21, p. 2634, Oct. 2021.
- [14] T. Cho and J. P. Bello, “Real-time implementation of hmm-based chord estimation in music audio,” in *Proc. of the Int. Computer Music Conf. (ICMC)*, 2009, pp. 16–21.
- [15] A. Stark and M. Plumbley, “Real-time chord recognition for live performance,” in *Proc. of the Int. Computer Music Conf. (ICMC)*, 2009, pp. 85–88.
- [16] F. Korzeniewski and G. Widmer, “Audio chord recognition with recurrent neural networks,” in *Proc. of the 14th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2013.
- [17] T. Hori, K. Nakamura, and S. Sagayama, “Music chord recognition from audio data using bidirectional encoder-decoder lstms,” in *Asia-Pacific Signal and Information Processing Assoc. Annu. Summit and Conf. (APSIPA ASC)*, 2017.
- [18] F. Korzeniewski and G. Widmer, “A fully convolutional deep auditory model for musical chord recognition,” in *26th IEEE Int. Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing (MLSP)*, 2016.
- [19] T. Carsault, J. Nika, and P. Esling, “Using musical relationships between chord labels in automatic chord extraction tasks,” in *Proc. of the 19th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2018.
- [20] B. McFee and J. P. Bello, “Structured training for large vocabulary chord recognition,” in *Proc. of the 18th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2017.
- [21] E. Tsunoo, Y. Kashiwagi, T. Kumakura, and S. Watanabe, “Transformer asr with contextual block processing,” in *IEEE Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding Workshop (ASRU)*, 2019, pp. 427–433.
- [22] E. Tsunoo, K. Yosuke, and S. Watanabe, “Streaming transformer asr with blockwise synchronous beam search,” in *2021 IEEE Spoken Language Technology Workshop (SLT)*. IEEE, 2021.
- [23] J. J. Bharucha and K. Stoeckig, “Reaction time and musical expectancy: Priming of chords,” *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 403–410, Dec. 1986.
- [24] F. Korzeniewski and G. Widmer, “Feature learning for chord recognition: The deep chroma extractor,” in *Proc. of the 17th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2016.
- [25] J. D. Lafferty, A. McCallum, and F. C. N. Pereira, “Conditional random fields: Probabilistic models for segmenting and labeling sequence data,” in *Proc. of the 18th Int. Conf. on Machine Learning (ICML)*, 2001, pp. 282–289.
- [26] D. Povey, H. Hadian, and P. Ghahremani, “A time-restricted self attention layer for asr,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2018, pp. 5874–5878.
- [27] W. Chan and I. Lane, “On online attention-based speech recognition and joint mandarin character-pinyin training,” in *Interspeech*, 2016, pp. 3404–3408.
- [28] C.-C. Chiu and C. Raffel, “Monotonic chunkwise attention,” in *Int. Conf. on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2018.
- [29] L. Dong, F. Wang, and B. Xu, “Self-attention aligner: A latency-control end-to-end model for asr using self-attention network and chunk-hopping,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2019, pp. 5656–5660.
- [30] C. Wu, Y. Wang, Y. Shi, C.-F. Yeh, and F. Zhang, “Streaming transformer-based acoustic models using self-attention with augmented memory,” in *Interspeech*, 2020, pp. 2132–2136.
- [31] Y. Shi, Y. Wang, C. Wu, C.-F. Yeh, J. Chan, F. Zhang, D. Le, and M. Seltzer, “Emformer: Efficient memory transformer based acoustic model for low latency

- streaming speech recognition,” in *Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2021, pp. 6783–6787.
- [32] C.-Z. A. Huang, A. Vaswani, J. Uszkoreit, N. Shazeer, I. Simon, C. Hawthorne, A. M. Dai, M. D. Hoffman, M. Dinculescu, and D. Eck, “Music transformer,” in *Int. Conf. on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2018.
- [33] Z. Dai, Z. Yang, Y. Yang, J. Carbonell, Q. V. Le, and R. Salakhutdinov, “Transformer-xl: Attentive language models beyond a fixed-length context,” in *Proc. of the 57th Annu. Meeting of the Assoc. for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, 2019, pp. 2978–2988.
- [34] L. J. Ba, R. Kiros, and G. E. Hinton, “Layer normalization,” *arXiv preprint*, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1607.06450>
- [35] N. Srivastava, G. E. Hinton, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. Salakhutdinov, “Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research (JMLR)*, pp. 1929–1958, 2014.
- [36] R. Cohn, “Neo-riemannian operations, parsimonious trichords, and their ‘tonnetz’ representations,” *Journal of Music Theory*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 1–66, 1997.
- [37] B. D. Giorgi, M. Zanoni, A. Sarti, and S. Tubaro, “Automatic chord recognition based on the probabilistic modeling of diatonic modal harmony,” in *Proc. of the 8th Int. Workshop on Multidimensional Systems (nDS)*, 2013.
- [38] L. Liu, H. Jiang, P. He, W. Chen, X. Liu, J. Gao, and J. Han, “On the variance of the adaptive learning rate and beyond,” in *Int. Conf. on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2020.
- [39] M. R. Zhang, J. Lucas, J. Ba, and G. E. Hinton, “Lookahead optimizer: K steps forward, 1 step back,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2019.
- [40] C. Raffel, B. McFee, E. J. Humphrey, J. Salamon, O. Nieto, D. Liang, and D. P. W. Ellis, “mireval: A transparent implementation of common mir metrics,” in *Proc. of the 15th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2014.
- [41] M. Mauch and S. Dixon, “Simultaneous estimation of chords and musical context from audio,” *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing (TASLP)*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1280–1289, Sep. 2009.